

Developing Strategies on Wellness Hotel In Northern Thailand.

Susaraporn Tangtenglam¹ Chonchanok Chidprasert²

^{1&2}(Faculty of Liberal Arts and Science Kasetsart University Kamphaeng Sean Campus, Thailand.)

ABSTRACT: This paper aimed to study developing strategies on wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. The sample group consisted of 4 and 5 hold business industry entrepreneurs (400 persons) in Northern Thailand. They were obtained by convenience sampling and did not rely on possibility. A set of questionnaires was used for data collection and analyzed by using descriptive statistics. Also, there was an analysis of relationships of guidelines for developing marketing strategies having an effect on wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. An analysis of correlation coefficient value and multi-stage multiple regression analysis were employed. Results of the study revealed that marketing strategies on product (X_1) ($\beta = 0.426$, $\alpha < .01$) and marketing strategies on personnel (X_5) ($\beta = 0.179$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the success of wellness hotel business in Northern Thailand

KEYWORDS - developing ; strategy; wellness hotel.

I. INTRODUCTION

Travel to visit beautiful sights in the beautiful. Natural and cultural attractions Which has a purpose To learn about life and recreation By dividing time from tourism For health promotion activities and / or rehabilitation therapy Such as getting advice on health Proper exercise, massage / steaming / herbal compress, meditation practice as well as physical examination. Medical treatment and others by tourism with consciousness to promote and preserve health and environment In general, Health Tourism has organized a program to relax in the midst of nature. To learn how to use energy From nature to heal, cure and promote physical and mental health Make it fresh and bright. In strengthening one's strength balancing the state of mind and body.[1]

In 2014-2016, Thailand's health tourism saw an average annual growth rate of 7%, with an average annual income of approximately US \$ 9.2 million. And expected that in 2018 there will be tourists For health from international countries, one million visitors come to Thailand [2] Other factors that positively affect tourism Thai health also has reasonable medical expenses for the services that customers receive. Thai hospitality with hospitable Thai cuisine comprising a variety of healthy herbs. Thai traditional medicine and Thai massage. Moreover, the increase of non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, obesity, head disease in the past 20 years has made the general public more inclined to care for health year Health promotion activities such as spas, food and wellness products become an integral part of the lifestyle of The lifestyles of people around the world therefore provide an opportunity for tourism-related businesses such as hotels and accommodation to Develop activities and products to promote health for tourists who are staying at[3]

Popular countries for The health care providers from the United States are India, Malaysia, Thailand and Turkey, respectively. Thailand is the most popular for health travelers. For those traveling for the health of Emirates Republic [4] From the performance index to Bloomberg Health Care Efficient Index (BHCEI) ranked A country with a population of 5 million or more and an average population of more than 70 years and a GDP of more than \$ 5,000 per year. Thailand ranked 27th (Up from No. 41 in 2017) of BHCEI from 56 countries worldwide, making it the ninth in Asia after Hong Kong, Singapore, South Korea, Japan, Australia, Taiwan,

New Zealand and the People's Republic of China. China It is also worth noting that Thailand ranks BHCEI better than many developed countries, for example, Netherlands in 28th, UK number 35, Denmark number 41, Germany. No. 45 and USA No. 54 [5]

Strategy to develop Thailand as an international health center (2016-2025) The Upper North is a region that has the potential for tourism, both culturally Various tourist attractions It is the center of economy, transport, education, as well as the hospitableness of the people in the area. More groups of tourists are interested in Wellness Tourism and Long Stay. It is a big market that is interesting. And a market with great potential Especially foreigners who retire more than 30,000 people foreign groups, including Japanese as the main target group. And westerners are interested in coming to stay for a long time in the North. Which plays an important role in stimulating the tourism economy of the northern region It is a travel channel that Thailand has to prepare for the hospitality. Because it is a quality market And has a higher purchasing power in tourism than the general market Which must select tourism products to meet the needs of consumers And adding more facilities to accommodate the expansion of tourism. [6]

Upper North of Thailand The Upper North has focused on promoting various types of tourism. To create a wide variety of tourism products for tourists and to increase the tourism potential of the North. By developing tourism for quality and sustainability There is a service business continually with high standard of tourism, healthcare and education. Including creative products that create added value Especially in the field of health tourism In line with the proposal of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports that promotes [7]

As a result, more groups of tourists are interested in Wellness Tourism and Long Stay. It is interested in doing research on developing strategies on wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. To be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for wellness hotel in Northern Thailand and to build confidence in foreign tourists. This could enable economic recovery in the service industry to return to normal and rapid growth.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study developing strategies on wellness hotel in Northern Thailand.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study marketing strategies that affect the developing strategies on wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was the 4-star and 5-star hotel operators in Northern Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between June - October 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about marketing developing on wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. The content consisted of 4 parts as follows.

Part 1 : General data of the respondents' hotel i.e. location, wellness hotel class and a number of rooms

Part 2 : Data related to guidelines for developing wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. standards leading to wellness industry.

Part 3 : Data related to relationships of the guidelines.

Part 4 : Problems encountered and suggestions about the guidelines.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the developing wellness hotel in Northern Thailand. and the set of results by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Table 1 Results develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand

Marketing	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE	β
x ₁ : product	0.349	0.042	0.436**	0.418	0.067	0.426**
x ₅ personnel				0.542	0.086	0.179*
R ²		0.345			0.413	
R ² Change					0.051	
F for change in R ²					4.645*	

Dependent Variable : develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand (Y) * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

According to Table 1, it was found that the develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand on product (X₁) ($\beta = 0.426$, $\alpha < .01$) and personnel (X₅) ($\beta = 0.179$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the elevation of international standards leading to wellness industry with a statistical significance level. This could be explained that variance of guidelines for develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand to elevate international standards leading to wellness industry for (R² = 0.345). The predicting equation of the guidelines as a holistic dimension (Y) in the form of standard score was $Z_y = 0.426Z_{x_2} + 0.519Z_{x_3}$

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that overall marketing develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand on product (X₁) ($\beta = 0.426$, $\alpha < .01$) and personnel (X₅) ($\beta = 0.179$, $\alpha < .05$) had an effect on the elevation of international standards leading to wellness industry with a statistical significance level. This could be explained that variance of guidelines for develop wellness hotel in Northern Thailand to elevate international standards leading to wellness industry for (R² = 0.345). The predicting equation of the guidelines as a holistic dimension (Y) in the form of standard score was $Z_y = 0.426Z_{x_2} + 0.519Z_{x_3}$ This conformed to a study of Manerot [8] which found that marketing factors comprised the following : the expenses for medical treatment in Thailand is lower than other countries; promotion of Thai medical tourism abroad; and good quality of Thai medicine (Brand image). For organizational factors and managerial administration, the Thai government has a clear policy on the promotion of medical tourism. Meanwhile, personnel factors comprise professional management because it is mostly private hospitals having readiness on specialist doctors and friendly service. This also conformed to a study of Theeranon [9] which found that Thailand has competitive advantage in terms of readiness in medical service and tourism with high standard of services. Besides, it was found that hospitals in Thailand are certified most in Asia on the basis of international standards (Join Commission International : JCI). It also conformed to the World Economic Forum [10] which revealed that Thailand had advantage in health service since the country is well accepted by foreign tourists in terms of health service resulting in the continual expansion of wellness tourism.

III. CONCLUSION

Developing and promoting Thailand as a tourism hub Healthy for The strategy to develop Thailand as an international health center for 10 years (2016-2025) and towards the center of medical & wellness tourism is moving effectively. Tourist market Global health is valued at 1.6 trillion baht, expanding almost 10 percent yearly, helping to generate income for entrepreneurs. Health tourism (Wellness Tourism) links and promotes All tourism groups have the fourth highest market value after cultural tourism, food tourism. And ecotourism Its income from health tourism accounts for 15.6% of overall tourism revenue. And has a relatively high growth rate, average 7.5% per year between 2015-2020. One cause come From the health tourism group of well-educated Moderate to high status with a long number of days to stay And the average spending per trip is higher than that of general tourists. Tourism has elements for There are many important aspects both condition Physical and service that tourists expect to be met, such as surroundings and natural beauty and culture Calm and pleasant place To relax in your free time from missions, convenient services to relieve stress. Benefit in improving health and Body and mind Overall a sense of security and care, water / hot springs treatment, service by skilled and trained personnel. And value for money.

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